

THE NEED TO REFORM ORGANIZATIONAL AND MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND IMPLEMENT NEW PRINCIPLES TO THEM

Boymirzayeva Dilbar Dmitrievna

Namangan davlat universiteti doktoranti

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258949>

Annotation: In this article, the training of qualified and competitive personnel in the higher education system is an urgent socio-economic issue, and the introduction of new approaches to the organization and management of educational activities in the higher education system, personnel training and continuous education system, the dynamics of development and structural changes of state and non-state educational institutions are expressed.

Key words and phrases: higher education, leaders-employees, modern worldview, scientific-theoretical views, continuous education, management tasks, perfect person, educational standards, civil society, scientific-methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in many countries, one of the urgent tasks is to develop and reform the principles of effective management in order to make education open to the majority, to have equal opportunities, and to contribute to its effectiveness. In this regard, many scientific studies, legislative and organizational reforms are being carried out to create a perfect system of higher education based on the institutional free functioning of all its activities on the basis of market laws.

Based on these reforms, it is necessary to create competition in the system by liberalizing higher education management, abandoning centralized management, giving academic independence to universities and creating financial freedom. In addition, it is necessary to organize the educational process in higher education institutions based on their capabilities, to develop and regularly update educational programs, and in general to increase creativity while abandoning standard educational programs. Already, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 11, 2019 No. PQ-4391 "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary special education" [1] - aimed at bringing the implementation of research and other organizational issues to a new level. Because the life of a modern developed society today cannot be imagined without the development of science and education. Therefore, the development of education in the leading countries of the world is defined as the first task. After all, the development of the country is closely related to its achievements in this field.

In recent years, the quality of education in higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan has been further improved, and the quality of our people's pursuit of knowledge, which has been formed over the centuries, is being reawakened and directed to high goals. As a result, it is ensured in every way that our young people achieve their dreams and goals, live a healthy and beautiful life, and get a permanent job in their profession.

The word control usually means actively influencing a controlled object or system to achieve a specific goal. This, in turn, represents a certain planned activity. Any activity consists of managed object and managing subject systems, and the communication between these systems is formed by human interactions, and the existing interactions represent their activities. Therefore, voluntary activity necessarily requires management, in the individual activity of a person, a person manages himself and achieves the desired results, interaction or the influence of a person on other people is necessary for the organization of cooperative activities. , which in its essence represents management, that is, the organization and coordination of human activities in the direction of achieving a certain goal.

Due to the emergence of the science of cybernetics, management research has developed rapidly, and scientifically based recommendations for managing a complex structure have begun to be put into practice. Management knowledge is considered to be the main source reflecting the needs of the time in many ways. The management process, on the one hand, ensures the integrity of the structure, and on the other hand, allows for its further improvement and development. Here, two main functions of management are distinguished: goal-directing and organizational functions".[3] Therefore, it follows that the work of the right management will lead to the improvement of the structure, and the wrong management will lead to decline. Therefore, choosing the right management model based on the specifics of each structure and conducting its functions in an orderly manner determines efficiency.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

German scientists V.Zigert and L.Lang defined management as follows: - "Management is such a way of managing people and using funds that it ensures humane, economic and rational achievement of the set goal. According to the point of view of the American scientist P. Drucker, - management is an intangible type of activity that transforms the crowd into an effective, goal-oriented and productive group".[5] In general, it is necessary to develop leadership culture and ethics in every sector of our society, to develop a system of taking into account the development of certain knowledge and skills when appointing a leader. Because leadership is a responsibility, responsibility and test, the personality of the leader should have knowledge, ability and initiative. Therefore, "management culture is a set of cultural and educational activities aimed at realizing a certain goal in the field of management and the process of their implementation. Management culture is applied to any managed object. That is why we can observe management culture in the management of society and in the management of organizations and institutions".[6] At the same time, one should not forget the humanistic task of leadership. Even if it is, trying to ensure the happiness of the governed. The famous thinker Abu Nasr Forbiy expresses the following opinion about this: "It is not possible for everyone - to lead others and raise them to the level of happiness. A person who does not have the ability to inspire someone to achieve happiness, to do necessary work, and is powerless to carry out this work, such a person cannot be a leader at all." [7] Also, Kaikovus, who is famous for his work "Nightmare", focuses on management and leadership issues. For example, "O child, if you are a king, be a beggar and keep your eyes and hands away from women and women of the people. Whatever you do, do it with the command of reason and do not act without advice, because the king's ministers are reason. Know the measure of each work and do all work thoughtfully. Look at all actions and words with the face of reason, so that you cannot see falsehood. Don't ask for anything bad from anyone and be kind to the

servants, but don't show mercy to the merciless. Always practice grace and kindness, but be politic.

Positive and negative factors can be distinguished according to their impact on the institution. If the positive factors serve to increase the management efficiency of the educational institution, the negative factors prevent a positive change in efficiency. There are factors that equally affect the management efficiency of any educational institution. Among such universal factors, the following can be listed:

☒ the quality of the goals;

☒ the possibility of realistic realization of the goals, that is, their compatibility with the means of achieving the set goal;

☒ correct assessment of the current situation;

☒ In addition, the management process in the management system of educational institutions should be properly established, the concepts of its efficiency should be clearly distinguished, its content and essence should be revealed, the department rating model based on the method of hierarchies analysis in educational institutions should be developed, its basis on the methods of evaluating the effectiveness of the management process are factors influencing the achievement of high results in the evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational institution.

☒ Today, in the internal environment of the educational institution, there is a need for simple, convenient, flexible methods for evaluating the effectiveness of management at various levels. The effective application of multi-criteria complex analysis and evaluation methods aimed at identifying, analyzing and evaluating problems of various nature and ensuring the most optimal decision in the process of management of educational institutions is distinguished by its breadth of possibilities and perspective. A comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of the management process of an educational institution arouses interest in many market entities and its relevance is justified by the above considerations. It is important to organize the management process in higher education institutions, to determine the methods of evaluating its effectiveness, to research and improve the evaluation of the effectiveness of the management process based on the results of practical activities.

The effectiveness of the management of educational institutions can be evaluated through various indicators. On the one hand, the assessment of the effectiveness of management activities of educational institutions is carried out only with management indicators, on the other hand, the effectiveness of management is the dynamics of changes in pedagogical processes in the educational institution, the effectiveness of resources, the impact of the reforms being carried out for each person. related to the degree of mystery.

Today, many scientific works have been published on management culture and its role and importance in the life of a higher education institution. Among them, the scientific researches of several specialists in the field of educational institution management and some scientists who carried out scientific activities in this field are noteworthy for the fact that they are dedicated to the study of various aspects of the management culture in the educational institution. Taking into account the place of education in the life of the society, it should be said that the problems of researching the specific management culture of the educational institution, the formation of the culture of management organization, and the practical use of the potential of the personnel reserve are considered urgent today.

The same approach was recognized by the employees of OTM. It was specially recognized that the direction of comprehensive discussion, which is typical of the type of participatory management of the organization, corresponds to today's requirements. At the same time, it was emphasized that the solution of problems (with the help of open mutual cooperation), the expression of organizational principles of leadership (stimulation of communication and cooperation) in the directions of this type are fully compatible with the mission of the organization. For this reason, more attention is paid to the participative culture in the prospective type of organization management. Another promising activity is the search for new creative approaches to solving persistent problems. It was explained that another type of management that should be developed with the help of this factor is based on entrepreneurship.

UNESCO deals with the issues of increasing the quality of higher education and the competitiveness of personnel in the world, and the formation of intellectual activity. He pays special attention to the issues of raising the content of higher education to the international level, organizing modular education, and improving the personnel training system based on the introduction of advanced teaching methods. In particular, the emergence of integration processes and actions such as the "European Area of Higher Education" shows that higher education cannot develop within one country at the moment.[8] It should be noted that in 1994, UNESCO and the World Bank summarized their work on bringing higher education to a new level and published the report "Higher Education: Lessons from Experience", and in it the income level is average. It is important to note that increasing investment in education in developing countries, introducing new principles to education management will have a great effect, and most importantly, there is a need for urgent measures to invest funds in higher education. was recognized. In 2000, as a result of the joint initiatives of UNESCO and the World Bank, the report "Higher Education in Developing Countries: Threats and Prospects" was published in the press, and the importance of higher education in any overall development strategy was emphasized. In it, the importance of higher education for comprehensive development of countries, reduction of poverty was considered in all details, and the need to experiment with educational strategies proposed by research institutes was emphasized.

RESULTS

The views based on scientific approaches in educational management were further developed in the 30s of the 20th century and became widespread mainly in the United States, and the administrative methods of educational management during this period, by the end of this period, management based on the principles of human relations made a new direction and a fundamental turn. theory began to develop. According to the results of the "Hawthorne experiment" of one of the founders of this theory, E. Mayo and his colleagues J. Homans, M. Follett, A. Maslow, F. Roethlisberger, social and psychological factors are more important than physical factors to labor productivity. proven to be effective. According to the analysis, the theory of educational management has developed rapidly in foreign countries, in particular, Western European countries, the USA and Canada, Australia and New Zealand. During the long-term development and as a result of encountering several stages of change, it has become a scientific direction that occupies a special place in the field of the general theory of management.

The liberal model - (USA, Great Britain, Canada) is characterized by the large-scale autonomy of higher education institutions. In this, the role of the ministries of education and authorities will be to form parameters for the strategic advantage and development of the higher education system. The main part of management powers is concentrated in the hands of intermediary organizations, which can answer the task of licensing and accreditation of educational programs, ensuring the assessment of the quality of education, and allocating financial resources.

In the USA, the signs of institutional autonomy are quite clear, because here the market is important, which reduces the leading role of the state and provides multi-channel financing of American universities, which is supported by the state, along with various grants. , also receives income from projects and contracts, paid education, charity funds, and the sale of scientific and educational services. Boards of trustees play an important role as mediators between the university and society.

Within the framework of the centrist model (France, Germany, Russia, Ukraine), higher education institutions are autonomous in educational, research, administrative and financial activities from a legal point of view. In addition, the relations of the university with the state are governed by legislative acts, orders and manuals (instructions) of state administration bodies.

Structures and tasks of higher educational institutions, curricula and programs, despite the fact that they have been updated, to a certain extent, are determined on the basis of the educational management manuals of state bodies, and they solve urgent issues related to the activities of higher educational institutions.

DISCUSSION

On the basis of the experience gained in the field of higher education, the regulatory and legal documents of the legislation of Uzbekistan are constantly being improved. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" dated June 5, 2018 Decision No. 3775 to determine the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, higher education In order to modernize education, develop the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" Decree No. PF-5847 was issued. According to the decree, the implementation of the following in the higher education system is determined:

▣ Development of public-private partnership in the field of higher education, increasing the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, creating a healthy competitive environment in the field;

▣ Turning the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University into the flagship of our country's higher education institutions;

▪ ▣ At least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1000 places of the ranking of internationally

recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including Including the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions;

- ☒ Step-by-step transfer of the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions;
- ☒ To raise the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, to establish a system of highly qualified personnel training that will make a worthy contribution to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and will find their place in the labor market; etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in today's globalization conditions, global changes are also observed in education. Along with introducing innovative approaches to adapt education to the processes of globalization, introducing innovative standards, there is an increasing need to reform the management system and introduce new principles to it. Today, academic and financial autonomy as components of institutional autonomy are being formed as new principles for higher education management and are showing their effective aspects. Therefore, every country aiming to reform the higher education system should introduce these principles into its higher education management.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2018, -B. 6-7.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3160 "On increasing the effectiveness of spiritual educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level." // People's word. June 28, 2017.
3. Makhmudovna, A. Sh. (2022/3/4).Creative writing in grammar lessons. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 258-260
4. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/3/4).Working with Texts in Grammar Lessons.barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali,261-263
5. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/11/15).Lexical-Semantic Classification of Concepts Related to Wedding and Marriage,(11)146-149
6. Makhmudovna, A. Sh. (2022/3/4).Creative Writing In Grammar Lessons. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 258-260
7. Makhmudovna, A. Sh(2022/3/4).Working with Texts in Grammar Lessons.barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali,261-263
8. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/11/15).Lexical-Semantic Classification of Concepts Related to Wedding and Marriage,(11)146-149
9. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5106 "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan." Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 27, Article 607.
10. Anyushin S.V. Upravlenie vysshimi uchebnymi zavedeniyami (novye tendentsii). – M.: «Akademiya truda i sotsialnykh ottnosheniy», 2000. –S. 203.

11. Azizkho'jaeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent.: TDPU, 2003. - P. 234.

12. Ahmedova N.K. Improving the effectiveness of management activities of general secondary school heads. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. Tashkent. TDPU. -B. 11.

